

BUSINESS-DRIVEN SYSTEMIC SOLUTIONS
FOR SUSTAINABLE PLASTIC PACKAGING
REUSE SCHEMES IN MASS MARKET APPLICATIONS

STARTING DATE OF THE PROJECT: 01/09/2022 - DURATION: 42 MONTHS

POLICY BRIEF
REGULATORY GAPS AND BARRIERS IDENTIFIED

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This policy brief, based on the work of the European Buddie-pack project (Horizon Europe), presents the regulatory gaps and barriers that we identified along the project. This document puts into perspective the obstacles raised in 2023, the regulatory changes in the meantime and the progress of the demonstrations. It proposes public policy recommendations to address persistent regulatory gaps or barriers, so as to support economic players and to encourage adoption of reuse by businesses and consumers.

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THE CHALLENGE

Establish a common framework for the deployment of reusable plastic packaging in safe conditions:

- By guaranteeing their functional integrity and health safety throughout their life cycle.
- By meeting European regulatory criteria (Regulations EC 178/2002, EC 852/2004, EC 1935/2004 and EU 10/2011).
- By encouraging business players and consumers to change their packaging practices and supporting this change until full adoption.

WHY IT MATTERS

The European Union has included the reuse of packaging in the revision of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (PPWR). Reuse systems must meet health, functional, and economic requirements in order to become a credible alternative to single-use plastic packaging. The European BUDDIE-PACK project, part of the Horizon Europe programme (HORIZON-CL6-2021 -CIRCBI0-01), aimed to develop systemic solutions for the reuse of plastic packaging in mass consumption applications by proposing, in particular, protocols for verifying the safety, integrity, and durability of reusable plastic packaging (RPP).

However, this matter being still innovative, demonstrations which have been led during the Buddie-pack project should be also an opportunity to highlight potential regulatory gaps and barriers to a larger deployment.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1 POLICY RECOMMENDATION 1: PROVIDE A REGULATORY FRAMEWORK THAT IS FAVOURABLE TO CHANGING PRACTICES TOWARDS REUSE

Given that Member States are not all at the same level of adoption of packaging reuse, we recommend that the EU addresses the issue of harmonizing reuse criteria (minimum number of rotations, progression strategies, etc.) by legislating through a delegated act of the PPWR, directly applicable in all member states. Buddie-pack reusable take-away trays or refillable detergent bottles demonstrate that cross-border harmonisation matters: packaging designed and tested in France may face different recognition of reuse status or deposit rules in Germany or Spain, for example.

1 - In the current and quickly evolving context, it is important to clarify responsibilities throughout the packaging life cycle to reassure stakeholders (manufacturer, washer, pooler) and to define in EU food-contact and hygiene legislation who is responsible at each stage of the reuse chain.

- **First**, it reduces legal uncertainty. In the absence of clearly defined responsibilities under EU food-contact and hygiene legislation, stakeholders may be unsure who is liable in case of contamination, non-compliance, or product failure. This uncertainty can discourage investment and slow down the deployment of reuse systems.
- **Second**, it builds trust among stakeholders. Reuse requires coordination between actors who depend on each other's compliance (e.g. proper washing, safe handling, traceability). Clearly assigning responsibilities reassures each party that others are accountable for their part of the process, making collaboration more viable.
- **Third**, it ensures consumer safety. Reusable packaging circulates multiple times, increasing the importance of strict hygiene controls at each stage. Defining who is responsible for cleaning, inspection, and compliance helps guarantee that safety standards are consistently met.
- **Finally**, it supports the scaling of reuse systems across the EU. Harmonized rules on responsibilities make it easier to operate across borders, reduce fragmentation, and enable the free movement of reusable packaging within the internal market.

In short, without clear responsibility allocation, reuse systems face legal risks, operational inefficiencies, and trust barriers—all of which can significantly hinder their development.

2 - Implement reuse and set up procurement requirements in public institutions (schools, hospitals, etc.) to ensure users are familiar with it and facilitate its dissemination to other sectors. In France, for example, government agencies, local authorities, and their associations are required to purchase a certain percentage of goods that are reused or recycled (or contain recycled materials) – Article 58 of the Agec Act (anti-waste law).

3 - Reuse can seem like an abstract and invisible topic to the general public: this is why including in the PPWR some more binding guidance by using EU Green public procurement (GPP) criteria to require reusable packaging (e.g. reusable catering trays such as Buddie-pack's multi-portion trays) in public canteens and hospitals, would make it mainstream and socially visible.

4 - Given the high consumption, and sometimes illegal dumping, of packaging and cups at community, sporting or musical events, the introduction of binding measures specific to these events, such as the implementation of reusable packaging and mandatory on-site deposits, could demonstrate their short-term benefits to a wide audience and facilitate its wider dissemination. Here too, in order to avoid distortions of competition and to support the development of reuse, harmonised rules should be imposed through European regulations.

5 - Introduce minimum requirements in PPWR for deposit-return systems (DRS) for reusable packaging in events, based on simplified return infrastructure such as the Buddie-Pack tray collector used in retail in France.

To Provide a regulatory framework that is favourable to changing practices towards reuse, legislation is necessary to have obligations because directives are not binding enough therefore not taken into account. In addition to the commitment and motivation of the actors, these binding measures should constitute a lever for support to help them evolve their practices, in order to secure and embed these changes over time.

2 POLICY RECOMMENDATION 2: IMPLEMENT ECONOMIC INCENTIVES TO ENCOURAGE THE DEPLOYMENT OF REUSE THROUGHOUT THE VALUE CHAIN

Implement economic measures that make reusable packaging more attractive than single-use packaging: this includes (but should not be limited to) financial support for packaging producers, retailers and users, differentiated taxation, etc. Eco-modulation could be introduced in Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) so that reusable packaging pays significantly lower fees than single-use equivalents:

- For instance, in France, the 2024-2029 specifications for the EPR household packaging sector explicitly include bonuses for the contribution of reusable packaging.
- Another French example is the payment of a premium for incorporating recycled materials into products, under several extended producer responsibility (EPR) schemes. This premium is paid by eco-organizations to producers and is proportional to the part of materials incorporated. This mechanism therefore makes incorporation economically advantageous.

Our research (currently under review and described in Deliverable 2.3) outlines current practice with respect to using rewards and penalties to promote reusable packaging systems and shows that surcharges on single use increase engagement with reuse systems.

Reduce operational complexity by establishing voluntary drop-off points at retail locations. Retailers and take-away chains should also be supported in installing convenient return infrastructure, such as manual or automated collection points. This approach was successfully demonstrated in the Buddie-Pack project, where consumers were able to return reusable trays at a store through an on-site collection system.

3 POLICY RECOMMENDATION 3: FRAME THE PACKAGING ASSESSMENT, SO AS TO BOOST PUBLIC CONFIDENCE IN THE REUSABLE PACKAGING CHEMICAL SAFETY ASSESSMENT

Current regulations (EU 10/2011) define migration testing for plastic food-contact materials, but they do not address the specific constraints of reusable packaging, such as repeated washing, mechanical fatigue, or long-term ageing. Test methods for reusable articles should therefore be expanded to:

- Integrate mechanical, thermal and chemical stresses representative of repeated use and industrial washing cycles.
- Include the assessment of NIAS formed during ageing, such as degradation products or reaction by-products, for which no harmonised guidance currently exists.
- Consider contaminant sorption and desorption, a major risk identified during the Buddie-Pack demonstrations but not yet covered by EU legislation.
- Clarify how migration testing must be adapted for end-of-life condition testing, which is essential for reuse but absent from current regulations.

These technical modalities should be discussed and tested before approval, the ultimate goal being to amend Regulation 10/2011 with an harmonized standard.

Microplastic release is not addressed in current food-contact or packaging legislation. However, repeated mechanical stresses, ageing and washing cycles can generate microplastics. Buddie-Pack results highlight the need to:

- Develop harmonised methods for quantifying microplastic release from reusable packaging.
- Assess the potential impact on food safety and environmental discharge.
- Integrate microplastic release thresholds or performance criteria in future European regulations.

MICROBIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT

- Set microbiological goals for packaging washing to ensure the absence of biofilms and pathogens.
- Ensure its consistency with regulations relating to food hygiene: current hygiene regulations (EC 852/2004) apply to food establishments but do not define specific microbial criteria for reusable packaging nor standards for industrial washing validation.
- Align packaging hygiene requirements with those applied to food-contact surfaces and utensils.

ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT

- Make the placing on the market of packaging conditional on an assessment of its environmental impacts during its life cycle. Given that reuse implies a significant shift in consumption patterns, with potentially very different impacts depending on the conditions of use, an environmental assessment of the packaging based on a most probable standard scenario appears essential to justify its relevance and avoid counterproductive results. This assessment would, in reality, only concern reusable packaging.
- Require companies to conduct simplified, standardised LCAs using methodologies like those applied in Buddie-pack for trays, detergent bottles and takeaway containers.

CONCLUSION

The establishment of a robust and harmonised European regulation for reusable plastic packaging in the food sector is essential to guarantee its safety and acceptability, and to promote its deployment. The Buddie-pack project provides some regulatory tracks following the demonstrations which it coordinated. Public decision-makers have a key role to play in formalising this work in regulations, by creating favourable conditions to shifting practices, supporting economic and social incentives, and completing or aligning the goals of packaging, safety, and hygiene regulations.

EVIDENCE AND CONTEXTS

SUPPORTING EVIDENCE FOR RECOMMENDATION 1: A HARMONISED FRAMEWORK TO ENABLE REUSE

Buddie-pack demonstrations across multiple use cases (e.g. takeaway trays, refillable detergent bottles, retail return systems) confirm that reusable packaging systems are operationally feasible but sensitive to fragmentation in practices and system design.

Project results show that:

- Diverging system parameters (e.g. reuse definitions, deposit mechanisms, return logistics) limit scalability and replication across contexts (D2.1).
- Unclear allocation of roles and responsibilities across the reuse chain creates coordination challenges between actors (D3.1).

Demonstrations further indicate that:

- More standardised and interoperable systems improve operational efficiency and facilitate collaboration.
- Retail and collective settings are effective entry points to deploy reuse and familiarise users.

SUPPORTING EVIDENCE FOR RECOMMENDATION 2: ECONOMIC INCENTIVES TO SCALE REUSE SYSTEMS

Economic analyses within Buddie-pack show that reuse systems are viable but face structural economic barriers compared to single-use alternatives.

Key findings include:

- High upfront investments and operational complexity, particularly for reverse logistics and washing (D2.3).
- Profitability depends on high return rates, sufficient reuse cycles, and system scale (D2.3).

Behavioural insights from the project demonstrate that:

- Deposit-return mechanisms and financial incentives significantly increase participation and return rates.
- Conversely, additional costs on single-use options can accelerate the transition to reuse (D2.3).

Demonstrations also confirm that:

- Accessible return infrastructure, especially in retail environments, is critical to reduce user friction and ensure system performance.

SUPPORTING EVIDENCE FOR RECOMMENDATION 3: ROBUST ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORKS TO ENSURE SAFETY AND BUILD TRUST

Buddie-pack technical work shows that reusable packaging systems require adapted assessment approaches, particularly under repeated use conditions.

- Reusable plastics undergo ageing and repeated mechanical, thermal, and chemical stress, which may affect material integrity over time (D3.2).
- Testing identified specific risks such as contaminant sorption/desorption and the formation of degradation substances (NIAS) (D3.2).
- The project also points to potential microplastic release linked to repeated use, for which standardised measurement methods are still lacking.

From a hygiene perspective:

- Demonstrations confirm that effective washing ensures safety, but requires validated protocols and consistent operational performance (D3.1).

Environmental assessments conducted in the project show that:

- Reusable packaging can deliver environmental benefits, but only under certain conditions, including sufficient reuse cycles and optimised logistics.

REFERENCES

Deliverable 1.1: Report on legislative policy

Deliverable 2.1: Consumer interaction with reuse systems

Deliverable 2.2: Guidelines for the design of reusable plastic packaging to minimise concerns about contamination

Deliverable 2.3: Recommendations for businesses implementing reusable plastic packaging systems

Deliverable 3.1 : Report on new functional material for reusable packaging

Deliverable 3.2 : Production of reusable packaging following sets of design rules

www.buddie-pack.com

PARTNERS

CONTACTS

IPC - The Industrial Technical Centre for Plastics and Composites

Florence Isnard
Project coordinator
florence.isnard@ct-ipc.com
+33 (0)4 26 61 90 53
2 rue Pierre-et-Marie-Curie
01100 Bellignat - France
www.ct-ipc.com

ACTIA - The French Network for Food Technology Institutes

Gemma Cornuau
Dissemination leader
g.cornuau@actia-asso.eu
+33 (0)6 18 69 52 13
149 rue de Bercy - 75012 Paris - France
www.actia-asso.eu

ACTIA